

**PRIMARY GRADE STUDENTS VIVID OUTLOOK ELEMENTS
AND THE FORMATION OF THE NATIVE LANGUAGE OF STUDYING
THE ROLE**

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Annotatsiya: This article educational outlook form factors for primary grade students with language developing that go to teach, Uzbek language to teach the basis of the material that is the importance and t- il social phenomenon that is h to realizedoctrines of the word will go

Base words: outlook, language, social development, language of connection, community, fonetik, the vocabulary, the grammar, thought, communication.

Students education to give one of the tasks in one of them the outlook foster. This task solution in purpose according working doublesthe tak the condition of a reader growing a person as successful identities find. Below are shown the factors of language teaching with associated without training the outlook - forming method defines.

1. Language is a social phenomenon, the essence of its communication function is to provide the expression. In school, including the primary grades in language teaching of the leader of the direction of language learners communication function to carry out to understand to achieve.

2. Language with thinking are closely related ,the thought of the word by means of the occurrence of out. Language of thought is maxsuli mind himself out of lives.

3.Language and thought around our wrap when taking financial asset in

relation is secondary.

4.The language that all parties have a mutual dialektik tied and harmony , which is complex, with many facets with a phenomenon. Communication in the process of the language all of the side a is one of the effects, so the language itself only recently uncovered conditions carry out the communication function of the will.

The language of social significance for its communication , the function of fulfilling seems to be.

His society life role clearly to understand the help you give to:

1. The role of language in the educational process of students of each speech unit development it is necessary to ensure.

2.Readers of the language communication function of language, the basic units (fonema, morfema, words, word combinations, sentences)in the process of understanding the function of study.

3. Readers understand the communicative function of the language “a language every a person and in general society performs any role in life?” the question find the answer team, as well as a creative effect. The increase of age of the people towards the people at the language to understand the role of begin.

4. Views of governors of the latest language to primary school as a social phenomenon in the formation of the origin of language, in the language of the appearance of that word about their level suitable secret that doubleschib positive effect.

Language development the about section for primary grade students, horse, quality, number, verb word of the category, the word of the composition will be a big chance it has. Small ages of the readers of the language of the mastering process, check that show, language scientific look at the basis of form, its important link to know help will. In particular, readers of the word sound in the side with its vocabulary ,the meaning of the word morfem an composition with

the vocabulary ,the meaning of the word grammatical meaning with his certain words of the category of the relevant ministry, between connection , such as to know that the same goal is to serve the will. This connection language fonetik, vocabulary, words to be made and grammatical side of one effects that character which total that will connect the private view is. This while readers of the outlook in the formation of the great importance it has. Language knowledge to give readers the life experience to rely on is important. The teacher's theoretical synthesis at the stage of collection of materials needed in nature faktik also given knowledge to practice apply to for also the child's life ,to experience speech related to practice relies on. Language related knowledge study as a result of the readers of speech activity, the quality will change, onglilik of increases.

Native language learning in the process of outlook on the basis of forming the foundation material to teach English in the school in addressing the issue of separate expensive to have. The real side of the material and its ideological direction artistic ifodalilik the readers thinking activity to feel – feeling effect is. Around – the environment about knowledge expands to the language and it is of interest to the people who created them, nurture determines the quality of their personal. Therefore, in the process of language learning in the age of small educational outlook is based on the formation of the following factors of the teacher methodological approach for students to master pleasing the language of the knowledge system, students learn that knowledge method language learning on the basis of which is the material of knowledge in giving , committed for political and artistic expensive solution of the effect shows.

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